

Creativity and Competency of Leadership While Working With Problematic Staff

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ABSTRACT: The main proposals and conclusions of the Research are analyzed which about to educate the intellectual students and to create the healthy atmosphere in Higher Educational Institutions. The Results of the Research work is useful for carrying out seminar-training and create syllabus and using practice in the Higher Educational Institutions.

KEY WORDS: competency of leadership, problematic staff, Internal conflicts, higher educational institution

INTRODUCTION

One of the urgent problems facing the field of education today is the insufficient organization of work by the heads of higher educational institutions to achieve high productivity in the educational process on a scientific and methodological basis, the use of progressive and effective methods of pedagogical and modern information technologies for this purpose. In the administrative management activities of any higher educational institution conflicts arise as a consequence of the common mistakes and errors, when the user is unfair suited to the evaluation of teachers and their encouragement, guided by nepotism, parochialism and corruption similar principles, bad learns the regulations in force, not sufficiently aware of the work carried out in each of the directions of educational activities, do not have enough knowledge, experience or does not meet the requirements of problem personnel for creative and social activity, ideological and political maturity. The lack of leadership qualities such as enterprise, initiative, organization, lack of dedication, efficiency, skill, creativity often lead to a loss of respect for the team and other problems.

THE MAIN RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Conflicts and feuds between problem personnel and heads of higher educational institutions can arise as a result of subjective mistakes of employees in relationships, ignorance of job requirements and obligations. From this point of view, the following types of conflicts are distinguished:

Internal conflicts related to the personality itself-usually they are not studied directly within the framework of social psychology, such conflicts are considered the subject of general and pedagogical path psychology, they arise mainly due to contradictions in the experiences, desires and motives in the soul of one person, the appearance of contradictory and mutually exclusive thoughts. Such a conflict as a rule, it is known only to the individual, sometimes, when a person does not understand that his offense is the result of an internal conflict, a psychoanalyst or a pathopsychologist comes to his aid.

Conflict that arise between the individual and the group usually occur as a result of the attitudes and actions of the individual standards and measures etiquette of a group in which a person lives or accessed by, the variances of the expectations of the individual against group norms. If this happens in the workforce, the important factors may be the poor qualifications of the group members or the incompetent management activities of the management. This means that an unhealthy psychological and spiritual environment reigns in such a team, which leads to contradictions between the members of the group.

Inter-group conflicts and contradictions arise when disagreements cover two groups or more, one of the main factors is that they "interfere" with each other in achieving goals. Usually, members of certain formal, official groups indulge in organizing, the interests of small groups collide and, as a result, conflict situations arise. Such a situation, called "organizing" is also harmful from a socio-psychological point of view, and has an extremely negative impact on the spiritual environment of the whole team. Sometimes conflicts arise between the management or the official system of the collective and the informal grouping within this collective. It is necessary to distinguish such situations from a mismatch of interests based on healthy competition, for example, from the struggle between political parties.

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The basis of conflicts that arise as a result of subjective causes and factors are the actions of people themselves, their personal qualities, and contradictions in their needs, desires and beliefs. At the same time, you should take into account such situations when the decrees adopted by the management leave others dissatisfied, when their work is not appreciated, or when some people have a frankly scandalous temper.

The emergence of conflicts and disagreements in public life and interpersonal relationships is inevitable. Therefore, some scientists argue that conflicts and disagreements have not only negative, but also positive results. For example, G. Andreeva writes about the constructive results of some disagreements. In her opinion, the conflict that has arisen between two persons can sometimes call them to develop correct and mutually beneficial conclusions, to retreat when such cases occur again. On the other hand, interpersonal contradictions, outwardly based on mutual reproaches, can force a person to work tirelessly on himself in order to correct his temper. Such conflicts are considered constructive according to their consequences. In addition, the consequences of destructive conflicts are usually the emergence of interpersonal antagonism, a blow to the nervous system of the parties, as well as various diseases.

* Constructive conflicts:

In a constructive conflict, disagreements are directed in a positive direction. It helps you make informed decisions. Relationships within the team are developing.

* Destructive conflicts:

If the conflict has no basis, it is considered destructive.

The personal dignity of each of the parties comes to the fore; the true causes of the conflict remain on the side.

Functions of destructive and constructive conflicts.

Conflicts can perform positive or negative, good or bad features. As you know, troubles at work, ethnic strife, localism, general political differences and the corresponding struggle, depression and loss, misunderstandings and misunderstandings, lack of healthy interpersonal communication, lack of sociability and the ability to establish contacts at first glance resemble domestic scandals and strife, which are particularly harmful to the human psyche.

This means that conflicts over positive functions can be constructive, and conflicts over negative functions can be destructive. Pedagogical conflicts manifest themselves in the following varieties: between teacher and students, between student and student, between individual and group, between two opposing groups. Neutralizing pedagogical conflicts that arise in higher education institutions, analyzing and understanding the causes of their occurrence are extremely important for management. It is difficult to categorize all conflicts by their causes, but there is a popular division into three causal groups.

You can also remember that conflicts can be open and closed. However, at the heart of any conflict is the denial of compromise.

According to the researchers, in order to promptly resolve conflicts between problematic employee and Manager, between teacher and student, between student and student, between teacher and teacher, management should foster constructive consequences that will affect the development of the student society, the teaching staff and all staff in General. You can give as many examples as you like about the causes of any kind of conflict. For example, A. A. Bodalev in the work "Features of interpersonal communication as a factor possible conflicts " specifically examines some of the above types of conflicts and gives them the following characteristics:

"Student-Student" conflict. Such conflicts in the majority of cases arise from the claims on the leadership of certain students in the composition of the micro-group. Interpersonal conflicts usually occur between candidates for leadership and authority in the group and members of the microgroup who are able to successfully occupy the rank of leader. Conflict situations of this type usually begin with a failure on the part of each of the leaders to recognize the authority of a group member who considers him a competitor. In interpersonal conflicts, leaders usually involve a micro group in the conflict, which includes themselves, because of which the scale of the conflict increases many times. Only an experienced group leader can calm such conflicts, often with the assistance of the students' parents. Most random interpersonal conflicts can also be based on a disproportionate display of superiority between groups of girls and boys.

"Student-Teacher" conflict. Conflicts between students and teachers can arise for various reasons. For example, a student who has received an unfair assessment develops a negative attitude towards the teacher. In such cases, all students of the relevant group are involved in the conflict. Some teachers use two mutually exclusive strategies when evaluating students' knowledge. On the one hand, in order to establish a friendly relationship with students, they can lower the bar of requirements, on the other hand, the requirements, on the contrary, are raised and tightened for a more rigid and effective professional training of students. Any of these strategies still leads to conflict. Students demand high grades in return for their own active in the learning process and good academic performance. Moreover, students with poor academic performance are often hostile to teachers, while demanding high grades from them. Students' knowledge should be fairly evaluated. Only then, will there be no conflicts.

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“Teacher-Teacher” conflict. Conflict situations between teachers themselves arise not only because of their inappropriate temperament and misunderstanding, but also because of the low development of a person as an individual, a personality.

There are many methods and ways to identify and eliminate the causes of disagreements in higher education institutions. This can be seen in the following three situations.

“The Head-Teacher” conflict. In order to be above the various contradictions that arise in daily activities in close relationship with teachers, the head requires communication skills and impressive work experience. The basis of such skills is the use of technologies of humanity, the avoidance of mediocrity, and the establishment of a close dialogue with teachers. If the head does not look for ways to resolve differences between the parties bring teachers closer to each other, guide them to join solve emerging problems, look for common opinions, disagreements will tear the team apart from within.

CONCLUSION

Despite the differences between the tasks and social roles of managers and teachers, they are united by joint activities. Equality in the reputation of subjects and cooperation provides an opportunity to deeply study pedagogical processes and combine them with self-education.

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